

TOWARDS SIMULTANEOUS ELECTIONS: ASSESSING INDIA'S ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION PROPOSAL

Dr. Ravindra. R

Associate Professor and Head, Dept. of Political Science, Govt. First Grade College

Kuvempunagara, Mysore -570026 Email - ravivarma1920@gmail.com

Paper Received On: 20 MAY 2025

Peer Reviewed On: 24 JUNE 2025

Published On: 01 JULY 2025

Abstract

India's early democratic experience was influenced by colonial legislative councils and local elections. Historically after independence, India held simultaneous elections until the late 1960s when political disruptions began creating staggered electoral cycles. General elections at present are conducted separately for Parliament and state assembly when the incumbent government's tenure ends or gets dissolved for some reason. One Nation One Election is a proposal to synchronize elections for India's Lok Sabha, state assembly and local self-governments. Simultaneous elections ensure convenience, will ensure higher economic stability and growth and will prevent policy paralysis and enhance focus on governance. For a sustainable political environment, democracy needs the active participation of citizens. For a voter National and state issues may sound different. The sudden implementation of the One Nation One election system may pose many issues related to provincial autonomy, disturbances in regional political ambience and the requirement of constitutional amendments. Effective steps to preserve the ideology of federalism and synchronization of electoral cycles through consensus are essential for Indian democracy.

Keywords : *Democracy, Parliament, Election, Federalism, Governance*

Introduction: Elections in India are the basic foundation of our rich and sustained democracy. Through political participation, we express our political views and elect political leaders to express their views, at the same time we have a voice in government operations. At the time of Indian independence, we enforced our constitution to guide the government and to protect the rights of the citizens. Since Independence, we opted for a multi-party quasi-federal structured Parliamentary form of Government to rule our country. In India, elections to Lok Sabha, Rajya Sabha, state assemblies and local self-government play a crucial role in

creating public opinion towards the government as well as the development of the nation. The concept of One Nation One Election refers to the idea of holding simultaneous elections for Lok Sabha and state legislative assembly across India. Though the concept of simultaneous election was visible during the early years of post-independence, the government aims to streamline the process of election to reduce cost and minimize the disturbances caused by the frequent elections in different states. The idea of One Nation One Election has several path-breaking benefits of bringing efficiency in governance, reducing the administrative burden cutting down the cost related to logistics manpower security and enabling governments to focus more on development rather than on constant election mode. However, it is not so easy to implement the idea of One Nation One election since it faces several challenges including the need for significant constitutional amendments and logistical changes. Indian states are created on the principle of federalism, States opinion and confidence must be taken before making any changes regarding the system of election.

Objectives

- To analyse the historical context and evolution of simultaneous elections in India
- To assess the potential benefit of implementing One Nation One Election
- To examine the potential challenges associated to One Nation One Election
- To propose the suggestions for effective implementation of One Nation One Election

Analysing the historical context and evolution of simultaneous elections in India

The idea of One Nation One Election has gained significant attraction in the Indian political arena, especially after the submission of a high-level committee chaired by our former president Sri Ramanath Kovind. One Nation One election refers to the proposal of holding simultaneous elections throughout India for the Lok Sabha and all state legislative assemblies. It also includes local self-government elections such as those for panchayats and municipalities. The fundamental aim of these respective changes in conducting elections is to allow the electoral cycles across different levels of government within a set time frame. Following India's independence in 1947, the country held its first general election in 1952 after the enforcement of the constitution of India. Since Indians live in the concept of unity in diversity, conducting elections for a vast parliamentary system of government is influenced by the United Kingdom. India has experienced synchronised elections from 1951 to 1967. The elections for Lok Sabha and state assembly were held in 1951-52, 1957, 1962 and 1967. During this period elections for the Lok Sabha and the most of state assemblies were held

simultaneously. This synchrony of elections provided a coherent political structure and reduced the logistical burden of elections.

The divergence in election cycles started from 1968 onwards, simultaneous elections were disrupted a state assembly dissolved at different times due to political instability and the imposition of presidential rule in some states. The premature dissolution of state governments in 1968 and 1969 as well as the earlier termination of the Lok Sabha itself in 1970 broked the synchronization of the Indian Election System. By 1971 elections for the Lok Sabha and state assemblies were no longer aligned, leading to the staggered almost continuous election cycle.

Voter turnout from 1st Lok Sabha to 18th Lok Sabha India

Election Year	Loksabha	Total seats	Turnout
1951-52	First	489	44.87%
1957	Second	494	44.44%
1962	Third	494	55.42%
1967	Fourth	520	61.04%
1971	Fifth	518	55.27%
1977	Sixth	542	60.49%
1980	Seventh	529	56.92%
1984	Eighth	541	64.01%
1989	Ninth	529	61.95%
1991	Tenth	534	56.73%
1996	Eleventh	543	57.94%
1998	Twelfth	543	61.97%
1999	Thirteenth	543	59.99%
2004	Fourteenth	543	58.07%
2009	Fifteenth	543	58.21%
2014	Sixteenth	543	66.44%
2019	Seventeenth	543	67.40%
2024	Eighteenth	543	66.33%

***Source: Wikipedia, General Election data**

From the above table we can analyse that voter turn out is very less in India during general elections from 1951-52 to 2024, even though wide spread of education and awareness about political participation.

At present only a few states and union territories such as Andhra Pradesh, Sikkim, Odisha, Maharashtra, Haryana, Jammu Kashmir and Jharkhand vote in the first and second half of a general election year.

Potential benefits of One Nation One Election System

One Nation One election refers to the proposal of holding simultaneous elections were the Lok Sabha and all state legislative assemblies as well as local self-governments in India. The prime objective of this concept is to align the electoral cycles across different levels of

government, or within a set time frame. Following are the significant potential benefits of One Nation One Election System.

- The concept of One Nation One Election could streamline the election expenses by saving billions of rupees and reducing the demand on personnel, polling staff, election materials and security. Synchronization of elections will lead to financial and administrative efficiency in the country. The same amount can be utilized for the development and programs of the country. The cost of Lok Sabha elections in India has increased significantly rising from rupees 10.5 crore in the first election of 1951-52 to rupees 50,000 crore in the 2019 general election.
- The One Nation One Election concept might allow voter governments to focus on policy frameworks rather than perpetual electioneering. Holding simultaneous elections will Foster better governance and stability which finally leads to national integration.
- Many times Federal concerns about popular democracy are visible during the implementation of governmental plans. However local issues cannot be sidelined in the name of national integration as the constitution is the supreme protector of federal units of India.
- Another potential factor of One Nation One Election is to guarantee a stable government. This would mean fewer disruptions to public life, benefitting educational institutions often used as polling stations, and government officials industrial in election duties and training by disrupting their actual duties.
- Simultaneous elections will reduce the election fatigue nature of youngsters which will lead to higher turnout and voter engagement during elections. A synchronized election cycle might make it easier for citizens to participate in both state and national elections at once as even today in rural areas or regions where travel to polling stations is challenging and stressful.
- Streamlined political campaigns will benefit even smaller parties to compete effectively with the national parties.
- One Nation One Election System will also strengthen the election commission of India by saving their time and multiplicity of work. This will lead to minimizing the duplication of work at the same time facilitate better election monitoring.
- One Nation One Election System will reduce election-related social polarization. Frequent elections often increase polarization as political parties compete in divisive

rhetoric to win support. Synchronization of elections will reduce the atmosphere of constant political competition fostering a more stable and less divisive environment.

However achieving these benefits would require constitutional reforms, political consensus and careful consideration of India's Federal diversity.

Major challenges of One Nation One Election System

Implementing One Nation One Election in India faces multiple challenges from constitutional and logistical barriers to political and practical issues, here we shall look at the main challenges.

- Synchronising National and state elections mainly overshadows the local issues as national issues agenda may dominate during the electoral discourse. Smaller Regional parties may find it difficult to compete with national parties. The idea of one Nation one election will pose a potential threat to the concept of federalism.
- To implement One Nation One Election would necessitate significant amendments to the Representation of peoples act, 1951. Key provisions in articles 83, 85, 172, 174, and 356 which define the term, dissolution, the emergency powers and amendment to the constitution will be altered.
- The synchronisation of elections nationwide may impact state autonomy. States should have less flexibility to address the local issues and needs independently of the central election cycle.
- Synchronisation of elections may skew campaigns towards National issues by overshadowing local issues. This could disadvantage regional political parties which focus primarily on state issues and lead to a more centralized Reform of governance as against to federal thought.
- Synchronization of election beneficial to the national party is especially rolling party at the center. Gaining political consensus across parties and States, particularly from the opposition and regional parties is challenging before the implementation of the One Nation One Election System.
- The Election commission in India requires significant resources to conduct elections including personnel electronic voting machines and security arrangements. Simultaneous elections nationwide would increase the demand for these resources all at once, potentially overwhelming the system.
- Addressing the issue of dissolution and political instability is more challenging.

Instability in state governments is a more common feature in our country leading to

Copyright © 2025, Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies

situations where a state assembly might dissolve before completing a full term. One Nation One Election would require creating mechanisms to handle early dissolutions, possibly through caretaker governments or other interim solutions.

- Implementation of One Nation One Election System will impact local representation and voter behavior. Voter behavior in simultaneous elections may be skewed by National issues with voter potentially voting the same way for both state and Central elections this could diminish the distinct identities of state elections and reduce the diversity in governance.

The above challenges highlight the complexity of implementing one Nation one Election System in a vast and diverse democracy like India. The decision requires thoughtful planning strong political consensus and solutions to the legal and logistical issues associated with such a shift.

Recommendations of various committee's regarding one Nation one Election System

- The recommendations of the high-level committee headed by former President Sri Ram Nath Kovind are as follows:
 - The committee recommended for a phased election. The first phase is to conduct Lok Sabha and State Assembly Elections simultaneously and the second phase folding for local body elections within 100 days of the first phase
 - The committee proposed 15 amendments to the constitution required in two Constitutional Amendment bills one for conducting Lok Sabha and state assembly simultaneously which will not require state ratification and another for local body elections which will require ratification by more than half of India's states.
 - The committee proposed to bring new constitutional articles such as 82A to facilitate the transition to simultaneous elections in India. Expansion of parliament power by amending article 327, articles 83 and 172 for handling early dissolutions of Lok Sabha and state assemblies, new article 324A to local bodies and Article 325 (2) to introduce the single electoral roll.

2. The Law Commission working paper(2018) has recommended to amend the constitution and the representation of the People's Act 1951 to enable simultaneous elections in India. Which also suggested modifying the anti-defection law to prevent stalemates in hung legislatures and act to extend the 6-month limit for issuing election notifications for added flexibility

3. Parliamentary Standing Committee on personnel, Public Grievances, Law and Justice (2015) has earlier emphasized the advantages of synchronized elections for better political stability and to save expensive resources.

4. The National Commission to review the Working of the Constitution (2002) has advocated for simultaneous election to promote continuity in governance.

5. NITI AAYOG's, working paper (2017) supports simultaneous elections to streamline the electoral process and strengthen Indian democracy.

Way forward to implement One Nation One Election System effectively :

Implementation of One Nation One Election system in India requires a careful approach that respects India's Federal diversity and practical challenges.

- Initially, voluntary synchronization of elections by gaining the support of States is essential without enforcing a nationwide change immediately. The Election Commission of India court groups state elections regionally and holds them simultaneously in phases that will achieve synchronization of elections gradually.
- Amendments to the key article such as 83, 85, 172, 174 and 356 of the Constitution of India should create provisions for fixed terms and mechanisms for dissolving both state and Central Governments simultaneously.
- There is also a need for defining roles for mid-term resolution introducing caretaker governments to manage governance if a state or the central government collapses in mid-term until the next scheduled elections.
- To prevent disruptions to the synchronized cycle of the election there should be a limit on no-confidence motions to specific periods.
- To strengthen the election commission's capacity, the government should concentrate on investment in technology for efficient voting processes better data management and coordination.
- The election commission should also establish a robust training infrastructure to ensure the efficiency of polling officials and security personnel.
- Political consensus building is very much essential factor to bring streamlining elections. Regular consultations with political parties and civil society groups can help to address concerns and identify practical solutions to resolve the issues arising out of the electoral process.
- To preserve local issues in elections encouragement should be given for local political parties to include state-specific manifestos and campaigns that address local concerns

within the broader National election cycle. It will reassure regional political parties and voters that local issues will not be overshadowed.

- In action with an awareness campaign can educate voters on the benefits and implications of the One Nation One Election System. This will address concerns about federalism representation and election processes. Voter engagement programs must be conducted to ensure that the public understands the concept of the One Nation One Election model and its impact on voting and how local and national issues will still receive balanced representation.

Conclusion

The concept of One Nation One Election presents a transformative vision for India's electoral process by promising benefits such as reduced costs and improved governance by streamlining Election cycles. The concept of One Nation One Election in India is not new but the implementation of this ideology will face several significant challenges including constitutional amendments and political complexities. Several States May the synchronization of elections in India will pose a threat to state autonomy. Balancing the efficiency of simultaneous elections with India's Federal structure and regional diversity requires careful consideration and consensus building. The concept of One Nation One Election offers a path toward a more cohesive and cost-effective Election System. But achieving the potential necessary dates a comprehensive approach that respects both democratic integrity and the autonomy of States. True strategic planning and inclusive dialogues with States One Nation One Election System could recap India's democracy to be more resilient responsive and sustainable.

References

R. K Jha; Indian Government and Politics, Pearson, New Delhi, 2012

Himanshu Roy and Mahendra Prasad Singh; Indian Political System, Pearson, NewDelhi,2018

<https://www.ndtv.com/india-news/one-nation-one-election-explained-what-is-it-how-will-it-work-6602206>

<https://www.drishtiias.com/daily-updates/daily-news-editorials/exploring-the-prospects-of-one-nation-one-election>

<https://forumias.com/blog/one-nation-one-election-explained-pointwise>

<https://artsandculture.google.com/story/india-39-s-first-general-election-1951-52/-wUhbZOT11a1RA?hl=en>